

Multi-stakeholder Intent-based service management automation for 6G Networks

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Abstract—This article presents a detailed intent-based framework with the objective to assist on the management of services and network resources in the current convoluted telco scenario. First, it introduces the context and complexity of telco systems to justify why intents may be required within the multi-stakeholder scenario with multiple and different actors (e.g., operators, providers, etc.). By removing the technicalities from the tenants' level and leaving them to the management system itself the approach aims to improve the interactions among all the actors and make the whole E2E control infrastructure more efficient. This paper illustrates the outcomes from the Hexa-X-II project on the management of intents with the main aspects and components of the designed framework and how they interact to reach a model in which the use of Close-Loops is key to manage each intent request individually while being coordinated with the others.

Keywords—component; Intent-Based Networks, Architecture, E2E Management, Automation

I. INTRODUCTION

Telco systems are complex, involving the administration, operation and maintenance (OAM) of a myriad of hardware and software resources that are i) deployed and installed in a distributed infrastructure; ii) combined into cloud and network functions, which collectively support the execution of end-to-end (E2E) communication services to multiple customers, from different market segments. The creation of simplicity out of this complex ecosystem requires applying the principles of abstraction and separation of concerns when designing these systems. Taking these recommendations into account, Tier-1 telcos (i.e., large mobile network operators worldwide) typically structure their OAM systems into different layers, each with a confined scope that can evolve independently from the rest of layers.

In the definition of actor-role model for 5G [1], 3GPP notes two main roles in telco ecosystem:

- Network Operator (NOP), focused on managing network and cloud resources, and their composition into upper-

layer network constructions, including domain-specific (e.g., sub-networks, network slice subnets) and E2E constructions (e.g., network slices).

- Communication Service Provider (CSP), focusing on building communication services and delivering them to targeted customers, including end-users (i.e., Business to Consumer -B2C-), enterprise customers (i.e., Business to Business -B2B-) or other CSPs (i.e., B2B to X -B2B2X-).

Tier-1 telcos typically embrace both roles, mapping them to different organization's units. In the telco system architecture pictured earlier, one can easily note that i) control layer is within the scope of NOP; ii) commercial layer is within the scope of CSP; iii) the network & service management layer is targeted by NOP and CSP, the former focusing on management of domain specific and E2E network constructions, and the latter on design, provisioning, and assurance of communication services.

In the 6G ecosystem, it is expected for Tier-1 telcos to become TechCos [2], with a wider scope on service offerings, and further flexibility on the composition and operation of managed resources. This means:

- TechCos service offering will not be limited to communication services (collection of PDU sessions exchanged between devices and data networks), but to other digital services (e.g., Web3, big data, security services). All these services will be also offered to new customers through APIs (instead of traditional channels). All this new scenario motivates the transition from CSP to a Digital Service Provider (DSP).
- TechCos will articulate their systems with much more granularity, breaking functions into their fundamental components (microservices), each representing stand-alone capabilities that can be individually programmed and chained on a per service/use case needs. This, alongside the ever-increasing offloading models in telco industry (e.g., with new emerging actors such as TowerCos, FiberCos, neutral hosts), also motivates the

decomposition of the NOP role into capability operator (COP) and resource provider roles.

This paper presents how the Hexa-X-II EU project proposes to evolve the current frameworks towards a ‘TechCo’ framework, with a wider scope in terms of service offerings and flatter roles for multi-stakeholder 6G networks. Specifically, this paper shows the intent-based E2E service management automation framework designed within the project and focused on multi-stakeholder scenarios based on network as a service (NaaS) to manage and expose services to multiple tenants by using Intent-based (human-friendly easy-to-use) APIs.

II. E2E INTENT-BASED SERVICE MANAGEMENT AUTOMATION FRAMEWORK

As illustrated in Figure 1, the E2E intent-based service management automation framework developed in HEXA-X-II involves different actors and entities. With the objective to enable the transition to the “TechCo” ecosystem, the framework is designed with four layers: a) the Digital Service Customers (DSC) (i.e., tenants) on top, b) the DSP, which is an extension of the 5G CSP, c) the Capability Operator (COP) layer (e.g., Network, Cloud, AI, etc.) and, finally, d) the Resource Providers layer.

The DSP and the COP may belong to the same administrative domain (e.g. Telefónica or Orange), while the Resource providers can belong to third parties. Regarding the DSP, it is the main interlocutor with the different existing types of tenants. Within the proposed E2E vision, the following three different tenant types interacting with the DSP are defined:

1) Tenant-1 type: An aggregator tenant which includes actors such as Hyperscaler Marketplaces, Telco Consortiums, etc. that follow the B2B2X model and offer the intent-based services to a second type of tenants.

2) Tenant-2 type: This type of tenant regroups either Verticals following a B2B model such as an XR provider or Application Service Providers following a Business to Business to Consumer (B2B2C) model. These two possible

tenants obtain the intent-based services through the interaction of an aggregator (tenant-type 1).

3) Tenant-3 type: Verticals may be a third type of tenants having direct access to the offered intent-based services, for example banking companies.

These three types of tenants are able to interact (directly or not) with the DSP layer with the Intent-based Digital Service Manager (DSM) placed at the DSP layer through what is called as the Intent-DSC API. To do so, the tenants will have to generate and agree on the intent request [3][4] with the expected service and targets associated to deliver the service to the final user through a selected set of the available COPs and Resource Providers below. At the DSP layer, the DSM is placed at each single administrative domain leading the management (i.e., provisioning, monitoring, etc.) of intents using the resources offered in the layers below by the capability operators and providers through an Integration Fabric (IF) component as defined in [5].

While one single DSP has a lot of services to offer, it is expected that it will not always be able to deliver all services and for this reason, a federation approach was taken into consideration when designing the E2E DSM framework. For this reason, the latter includes the possibility to allow the interaction of different DSP through their Intent-based DSM, using an east-west interface called “Intent-DSP API”. Regarding the internal architecture of functionalities and capabilities offered by the Intent-based DSM, this topic is properly addressed in the following section.

The third identified actor within the framework are the COPs, which are operating those entities/elements in charge of managing the domain resources available. A COP is handling the control and management elements such as a Network Slice Management Function (NSMF) or other domains specific managers. Finally, the communication between the DSP and the COP layers is done through the IF.

Finally, the last layer involves the Resource Providers across different domains. The Resource Providers offer a set of different domain resources such as applications, AI, network (including RAN, transport, and core) and finally, cloud

Figure 1 - E2E Digital Service Management Framework.

resources (extreme-edge, edge, and cloud). The type of available resources to be managed that each single administrative domain has may vary depending on the needs, the previous figure illustrated shows one of the many possibilities that may exist.

III. INTENT-BASED DIGITAL SERVICE MANAGER FUNCTIONAL ARCHITECTURE

Based on the guidelines from the 3GPP [6][7] and as illustrated in Figure 2, the functional architecture of the proposed intent-based DSM called DSM-Intent Management Entity (IME) is structured in 7 functional blocks and interacts with the Service Management Domains (MDs) and the Resources MDs through a Cross-domain Integration Fabric (IF).

Internally, the DSM-IME has the following modules:

1) **Intent Interface:** The gateway for the user to interact with the whole intent management solution and the core element of the architecture as it takes care of the intents data objects with the multiple actions to control the intent’s life cycle. It offers the following capabilities: the “Intent Interpreter” to process the incoming requests from the user and let DSM-IME understand what is intended; the “Intent Handling Capability Exposure” which allows to the system to present to the user what the system is capable to offer and manage through the use of intents; the “Intent CRUD” (Create/Read/Updated/Delete) to offer the different set of operations to trigger the different processes to manage intents; the “Intent Activation/Deactivation” to activate and deactivate a deployed intent to make it functional or keep it in standby until it is required again; and finally, the “Intent Report Management” to offer the methods related to the expected reporting of intents in relation with the Intent Reporting functional block.

2) **Intent Fulfilment Internals:** This functional block is composed of capabilities that a user should never be able to access but that are key to those capabilities visible to the user. Among the capabilities in this module the “Intent Translation” takes care to map the the intent and its expected key

performance indicators (KPIs) and key value indicators (KVI) into a set of executable service management tasks and policies from a contracted SLA, the “Intent Feasibility Check” focuses on ensuring that a received intent request may be properly applied, the “Intent Closed Loop (CL) Governance and Coordination Service” has two main objectives: a) it takes care to trigger the necessary set of “Intent-driven CL Control for fulfilment evaluation” instances associated to each requested intent in order to ensure the correct deployment and to fulfill the expected requirements, and b) it offers the capability to control in a coordinated way the co-existence of multiple CLs [8] within the DSM-IME, and finally, the “Intent Conflict Detection/Resolution” aims to identify if a new intent or an action over an existing intent may affect negatively other existing intents and, in case there is a conflict between two or more intents, to resolve it.

3) **Intent Reporting:** This functional block offers three capabilities that focus on the multiple types of intent-related information. These are the “Intent Feasibility Check Information” that presents whether it is feasible to deploy an intent or not (e.g., with the current resources available), the “Intent Fulfilment Information” such as the intent fulfilment status and the associated target achieved values, and finally, the “Intent Conflict Information” with the associated conflicts and their resolution.

4) **Intent-driven CL Control for fulfilment evaluation:** This functional block offers the capabilities to manage the life cycle of the intent CL instances and ensure they are fulfilled at any time. Once an Intent CL instance is created, it has the following capabilities associated to it: a) the “Intent CL Governance Service” offers the orchestration capability to control any action involving its assigned intent instance, b) the “Intent CL Execution” executes any task commanded by the governance capability, c) the “Intent CL Analytics (KPI & KVI)” is the capability to process monitored metrics and generate insights from it, d) the “Intent CL Decision” makes use of the insights generated to select the most suitable decision about the intent CL instance status, e) the “Intent CL

Figure 2 - DMS-IME functional architecture.

Monitoring” is the capability to acquire data and metrics related to defined KPIs to be properly analyzed by the “Intent CL Analytics (KPI & KVI)” capability, and finally, f) the “Intent CL Data Services” is the capability to store the information-related to each specific intent CL instance.

5) Data Services: This functional block is in charge to store the intent data objects and other possible information such as Service Level Agreements (SLAs) and policies.

6) 3rd Party (3P) Profiling: This functional block allows providing a Hexa-X-II tenant (i.e., a 3rd party) full characterization through a 3P profile. This captures tenant-specific data on security (supported credentials and access control solutions), trustworthiness (relevant in federation scenarios), contracted services and SLAs, and end-users.

7) Service Portfolio: This functional block is focused on offering the available 6G services information to the tenants, so that based on the available services and their information, tenants may formulate more precise and adequate intent-requests. Available service information cover aspects such as service status (i.e., defined, designed, built, tested, released, etc.), owner, variabilities over the same service (i.e., SLA offerings, etc.), costs or dependencies with other services, etc.

Finally, as introduced previously, all these functional blocks interact with the Service MDs and Resource MDs to accomplish an E2E intent-based management of the service requested by the different tenants. As presented, the communications among the DSM-IME and the Service MDs and Resources MDs is done using a Cross-domain IF, which may allow the possibility to exchange information among different solutions using an harmonized protocol.

IV. INTENT-BASED DIGITAL SERVICE MANAGER WORKFLOW

Based on the architecture illustrated in Figure 2 and the guidelines in , the workflow in Figure 3 illustrates how intents are processed, fulfilled, and evaluated against KPIs and KVIs within the constraints of SLAs. The process includes the tasks to check for feasibility, monitoring, conflict detection and resolution, and reporting at various stages.

The workflow begins with the “intent request and feasibility check” phase, where a request for a specific intent is made (step 1). Once this intent request is received, it is processed, starting with the identification (step 2) of the requested services and their corresponding KPIs and KVIs using technologies such as Natural Language Processing (NLP). These identified KPIs/KVIs are then verified within the SLAs based on the tenant profile (step 3) with the 3P profiling.

Following the KPIs/KVIs verification, the intent is formally created and stored (step 4) and its status notified (step 5) to the intent requester (i.e., DSP/DSC). At this point, with the created intent object, an intent fulfilment request (step 6) is then mapped into a set of executable services and one or more closed-loop (CL) policies to meet the KPI/KVI as per the contracted SLA (step 7). With all this information, the feasibility of fulfilling the intent is checked (step 8), and a report object is created along with the specific feasibility reporting data (step 9).

The second phase in the workflow is the called “Intent closed-loop fulfilment and evaluation”. In this phase, a CL instantiation is triggered using the information of the previously selected policies (step 10). It is worth to mention that, depending on the policies, one or more CLs may be created to properly fulfil their specifications. The creation of a CL involves requesting service deployment to meet the

Figure 3 - Intent Provisioning and CL Management workflow.

KPIs/KVIs (step 11) and configuring (step 12) the resource management domain (MD). The system then responds to the service deployment request (step 13) and subscribes for monitoring parameters (step 14). Finally, the CL applies the last tasks before an intent may be considered fully deployed. The monitoring of the intent's parameters (step 15) is conducted, followed by an analysis of the KPIs/KVIs (step 16).

Based on the analysis, the CL must decide whether the intent KPIs/KVIs are accomplished or not. If KPIs/KVIs are not met (step 17), the workflow includes a decision point where the intent-related resources may be reconfigured based on the defined policy. Finally, to complete the fulfilment and evaluation phase, a reporting task is generated to document the current intent status (step 18).

Table 1 - Proposed enablers for the management of intents.

Enablers	Objectives	Description
Intent Translation & Provisioning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To reach an agreement with the user and create the intent data object. - To translate an intent into a set of machine-based requests depending on the different resource domain managers available behind the IF. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - An intent-based solution to manage service resources located across multiple domains and to select the most suitable combination of them to deploy the E2E service and to achieve the expectations and targets defined by the service requester, while keeping under consideration the specific characteristics of each involved domain. - The translations are done considering the service, security and trust levels and the constraints of the resource's domains.
Data fusion mechanisms based on telemetry data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To provide intent achieved values and support intent driven-orchestration. - An E2E mechanism for intent monitoring, analysis, decision-making and execution. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This enabler offers a collection of heterogeneous observability signals based on OpenTelemetry standards for the early identification of anomalies and causality analysis. Moreover, it supports application, network and infrastructure failure identification and mitigation actions and also assists with intent-based mechanisms at real-time and calculation of intent achieved values for intent fulfilment evaluation.
Closed Loop Coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Zero-touch coordination of multiple closed-loops generated for automatic intent management at the DSP level. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrated solutions for the automatic coordination of multiple CLs generated for the lifecycle management of the Intents. - Conflict resolution triggered by Intent Conflict Administration (ICA), while CL coordination maintains the logic required to enforce policies and configurations for the resolution/mitigation of the conflicts, following the instruction provided by the ICA
Intent Conflict Administration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To detect the conflict of intents. - To inform to the tenants about this conflict. - To provide solutions to manage the conflict of different intents. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Different Intents that are deployed in the network can have different KPIs that can impact negatively on different Intents resulting in Intent Conflict. - This enabler proposes solutions to manage these Intents conflicts automatically and inform to the respective tenants that a conflict is detected.
Human-machine intent interface design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To fulfil the need for intent-based interfaces that allow expression of application's needs and requirements to networks, as well as system insights, feedback and actionable items back to applications. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enablement of dynamic interactions between applications and networks where application's needs are expressed efficiently, not necessarily in a native network language, whereas networks can adapt to human and application inputs and provide timely and meaningful feedback
Intent-driven placement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To propose intent description extensions and associated analysis and decision mechanisms to steer high level (intra-DSP/cross-DSP) compute placement across the compute continuum 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Intent-based extensions to microservice descriptors to include target features of the infrastructure components on which these microservices are required to be deployed (or even explicit references to target execution domains) -Intent translation mechanisms for deriving the execution domain to contact and request orchestration from, while maintaining a closed-loop in charge of reacting to changes to adjust placement according to the intent expression
Declarative Intent Reconciliation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To ensure intent specifications and intent delivery workflows are consistent, up-to-date, and effectively translated into actionable configurations across multiple management domains. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This enabler employs a declarative approach to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - describe, modify and version-control intent specifications - define pipelines to streamline the intent life cycle management across intra-DSP or cross-DSP components operated by different stakeholders.
Intent Reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To provide the tenant (intent owner) with the ability to consume intent reports from DSP (intent handler). - Issues in scope of this enabler include which details an intent report should contain, and how these details can be captured into an information model. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It provides means for the tenant to verify and audit that the intent, processed by the DSP, gets fulfilled across the entire lifecycle. - The DSP reports on the progress according to the reporting conditions the tenant has specified.
3rd party facing services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide solutions that allows characterizing tenants (i.e. 3rd parties) and service offerings under the DSP realm, so the DSP can relate them for service delivery purposes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For each tenant accessing the Hexa-X-II system, the DSP creates and manages a 3rd party profile. - Service offerings are linked to tenants according to well-defined SLAs.

The last phase in the workflow is the “Intent conflict & Resolution”. In this phase, the CL KPIs/KVIs are frequently monitored (step 19) to identify any conflicts between one or more intents, in particular, when a new intent is being deployed or a re-configuration is done over an existing one that may affect another intent. The incoming data is analysed (step 20) and, if a conflict is detected (step 21), a conflict resolution is undertaken according to pre-defined policies. In this situation, it is important to take into account how to manage the conflicts as different approaches are possible. A conflict resolution model may be applied depending on who the intents producers (i.e., requester/owner) are. If two conflicted intents belong to the same intent producer or not, the conflict resolution decision may be left to the system itself (e.g., using priorities) or to the intent owner, who will have to decide what to do (e.g., modify or remove one intent or the other one). Independently of how the resolution model is applied, whenever there is a conflict, the intent report is updated with the conflict information (22). In case there were no conflicts, no report on this aspect is necessary. Finally, the workflow ensures that reporting is communicated effectively to the DSP/DSC (i.e., intent owner), including the feasibility, fulfilment, and any conflicts between requested and measured KPIs/KVIs, thus completing the intent management process (step 23).

V. PROPOSED INTENT-BASED ENABLERS

The presented framework, functional architecture and workflow are the starting point to define and build the elements necessary to achieve a complete management of intents that will allow to reach the level of autonomy desired for the near-future network management and control systems. To this end, the presented DSM-IME functional architecture was used to trigger the creation and first definition of a set of enablers presented in Table 1.

The different enablers are proposed to interact with and complement each other with the final goal to deploy, monitor and update intent-based services, removing the technical tasks complexity from the intent producer (i.e., DSP/DSC) and leaving it to the control system itself (i.e., intent handler). For example, based on the workflow presented in Figure 3 and in order to accomplish the actions defined from steps 1 to 9, an initial enabler interaction could be the one done among the “Intent Translation & Provisioning” (IT&P), the “3rd Party Services” (3PS), the “Human-machine intent interface design” (HMIID) and the “Intent-driven placement” (IDP). The IT&P should focus on the creation and management of the intent data object by calling the other enablers when required; requesting to the HMIID the proper interpretation of the incoming request if it does not have the right data model format (step 2). Then, it should request to the 3PS for the contracted SLAs and the verification of the KPIs/KVIs (step 3) and finally, as part of the possible feasibility options (step 8), request to the IDP the placement of the resources to implement the intent expectations.

After this first interaction, a second one would cover step 10 to 18, with the IT&P and “Closed Loop Coordination” (CLP) and the “Data fusion mechanisms based on telemetry

data” (DFMTD) in order to deploy the corresponding CLs (steps 11, 12, 13) and to monitor them (steps 14, 15).

Furthermore, the third and final interaction set would be the one between the IT&P and the “Intent Conflict Administration” (ICA) and the “Declarative Intent Reconciliation” (DIR). Among them, they could manage the actions related to the analysis and detection of conflicts (steps 19, 20) and their resolution (step 21).

Finally, there is one more possible interaction which is between all the previous enablers and the “Intent Reporting” (IR). In this case, the IR is not a key element on the provisioning actions to deliver a service nor the monitoring actions to detect conflicts, but it is a key element on achieving both of them as it supports them by managing the information generated and creating the intent reports objects that allow to identify where did an intent conflicted or to inform the intent owner of its fulfilment, at any moment of the intent life-cycle. This ensures that both the system and intent owner may act over the intent when this is not fulfilling its duty.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This article has described the initial elements to assist with the use of intent-based actions in a complex 6G ecosystem, which involves the participation of different and multiple stakeholders, increasing the complexity in considering the specificities of each one of them. To do so, the framework of an intent-based architecture, its main functionalities and the enablers that should make it possible were presented.

The future work will be focused on evolving the interaction between enablers and the internal architecture definition of the enablers and their external interfaces to properly ensure exchange of data.

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